

LINGUISTIC AND SOCIAL ANALYSIS OF EUPHEMISMS

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the linguistic analysis of euphemisms, why they are used in social spheres, the use of euphemisms in different situations.

A euphemism is an appropriate phrase or phrase used in place of words that may be found inappropriate or insulting. Euphemisms are often used in everyday language and literature to replace a language that some may not like. Euphemistic language is commonly used in the literature, especially in older works, as a method of conveying a message without compromising the possibility of censorship for rude language.

Euphemistic language can be found in both literature and everyday language. But a better understanding of the meaning of euphemism is used. While everyone uses euphemistic language as a means of conveying other things, the reason for the change may be different.

Avoid insulting words. In particular, in past conservative periods, euphemisms were commonly used in everyday conversations to avoid insulting and even taboo languages. The most common topics used in euphemistic language are death,

imprisonment, and male-female relationships.

Character traits. If a particular protagonist in a film or literature uses a euphemism, it can be seen that the character is more conservative or attentive to the use of inappropriate language. Saying the wrong version of the sentence is a direct manifestation of their characterization. For example, in A. Kadiriyy's book *The Last Days* "Otabek uylanganligini aytganida onasi uni koyib, seni o'sha Marg'ilonlik sehrigar «andi» o'z sehrig jodusiga olgan deb koyiganda ham Otabek ota-onasiga qarshi gap aytolmadi.", in the sentence "Ra'noni egasiga topshirmagunimizcha, — dedi Nigor oyim, — quyilmaydiganga o'xshaydi" (A. Kadiriyy) In other words, from the point of view of speech etiquette, the epiphany in the form of handing over to the owner is used instead of the word to give to the owner.

Euphemisms often change depending on the time of the story or appear more or less. If a novel, film, or

television takes place over a period of time, the euphemism can be used to describe the vernacular of the period. For example: Quvnoq alifbo or Happy alphabet (on Bolajon TV channel)

Diversity of language. Euphemisms are ways of using different words to say the same thing. This allows writers to add variety to their writing so that creativity and actions or phrases don't become monotonous. Euphemisms are poetic and can create images that literally can't do in language. For example, in Othello, Shakespeare uses the term "animal through two" as a euphemism for male and female relationships. This example creates more imagery and variety than just saying the two are in touch. In Uzbek, "yukli, og'ir oyoq" instead of "pregnant."

Euphemism is a common word or phrase in everyday language and conversation. They allow us to have awkward conversations without using annoying language. For example, when a boss tells an employee to "let go" instead of "dismiss" the goal is to soften the blow. about examples of euphemism in literature: George Orwell's 1984 work used euphemistic language within the story to describe the dystopian society's propaganda. In the book, "newspeak" became the official language of Oceania. He uses euphemisms like "joycamp" instead of "forced labor camp" as well as "Minipax" for "Minister of War".

The use of euphemistic language in 1984 effectively criticizes the government's attempts to mislead citizens through credible propaganda. Watts notes the euphemistic use of the word 'defense' has increased in modern times: after the Second World War, the U.S. Department of War became the Department of Defense

and, in 1964, the British War Office became the Ministry of Defense.

One of the reasons writers used the euphemisms we listed above was to mark the time period of the story. This is especially true when writing and creating a work of the period. Euphemism is not just a way to avoid rude words. They can be used in literature and screenwriting to both define social norms and critique them. As a writer, use euphemisms as a means of reflecting on the world you are creating and the characters you live in.

Types of Euphemism in Writing: Politeness. Impoliteness is usually regarded as a social taboo, which is why euphemisms act as mitigation tools that reduce the severity of the given situation. Diplomacy. Diplomatic discourse is a genuine art. Abstraction. Litotes. Spin euphemism. Conclusion.

The most frequently occurring euphemisms included metaphors (orange skin), metonymy (it, these, other), word-play (Roger Moore), irony (hell), and the like. For some time now, the marketing industry has been using the soft language of euphemism to overcome expressions that may offend consumers or suggest something unpleasant. Euphemisms are employed to avoid saying anything controversial, taboo, or indiscreet, and can be really witty and out-and-out comical at times.

A 'euphemism' is an indirect way of talking about something that might be rude, upsetting or taboo. We use euphemisms to make things sound better or, at least less offensive.

Types of advertising that euphemism are used. Newspaper. Newspaper advertising can promote your business to a wide range of customers.

Magazine. Advertising in a specialist magazine can reach your target market quickly and easily. Radio. Television. Directories. Outdoor and transit. Direct mail, catalogues and leaflets. Online.

Euphemisms are considered 'comfort words' as they are used to avoid discomfort and reduce tension when speaking to people but it is not good to use euphemisms in academic writing. Many style guides advise writers to avoid euphemisms informal reports and academic writing. What is a negative consequence of using a euphemism? It can minimize the seriousness of something. One communication strategy used by speakers is called "euphemism" which is "the extension of ordinary words and phrases to express unpleasant and embarrassing ideas" (Hudson, 2000, p. 261). Indeed, euphemism is considered as part of politeness and it deals with how to avoid being rude to others or too direct.

Euphemisms are fallacious because they are intentionally used to conceal the truth and obscure any real meaning; they are soft language used to mask or

downplay warranted emotional force. Being ambiguous or vague in meaning brands euphemisms as a type of weasel word.

In order to achieve spiritual maturity, it is necessary to use the language, which is a cultural heritage, appropriately, rationally and effectively, to study it deeply and to enjoy it. After all, the interaction of any person with the people in the environment in which he lives, his beliefs, adherence to traditions, aspirations, national values ensure the formation of his personality. Every aspect of this process is linked to language, or language acts as a tool in any situation.

It can be said that the need to express concepts that are morally and culturally unusable or found to be inappropriate in a more lenient manner, sometimes with the help of words, creates euphemisms, and each of the social strata is always created as a new invention. the value of euphemisms can be said to be a factor of their unusualness, urgency, of human reasoning.

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